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SOCIAL SECURITY FOR THE UNORGANISED SECTOR : NEED OF THE HOUR

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The Unorganised Sector : Definition and Issues : The unorganised sector is a much discussed concept these days. There are different views regarding the same. It is sometimes defined as the sector which is not recorded under any factory legislation. In this sense, it is derived as residual category after deducting the registered labour force from the total labour force. As the small and village industry is not generally registered, the unorganised sector is often identified with the small and village industry sector. But this is not fully correct as it presents only half of the picture. This is so because, this method doesn't cover the unorganised sector part working in the service sector. Besides, not all industries defined as small by the government are unregistered. Some of them are registered under the Factories Act.

The concept of the informal sector is usually applied to the urban system. This does not take into account of the production relations within the agriculture. The large, medium and semi-medium farms on which modern methods of management have been introduced may be considered under organised sector within agriculture. Besides, these need to be distinguished from the self employed small marginal farmers and casual labourers. Only the latter category, and not the whole of agriculture needs to be considered under the informal sector. Further, the inclusion of modern small-scale industry and powerlooms on the unorganised sector may not be considered appropriate.

Arthur Lewis in an article in 1950's propounded the *Theory of Dualism*. He was of the view that in due course of time, the unorganised sector with surplus labour gets absorbed in organised sector. In India the situation is quite different. The share of unorganised sector in National Income has been declining but the number in unorganised sector continues to swell. Despite several decades of post independence capitalist growth organised sector has not been able to absorb the labour force in the unorganised sector.

Earlier literature show that the approach to the unorganised sector was negative. This sector was considered unproductive which would gradually disappear with development. Recent literature show that activities in the unorganised sector are economically efficient and profitable as well. Though they are characterised by low level of productivity, a small and usually poor clientele, a low level of formal schooling, intermediate technology, preponderance of family labour and ownership and ease of

entrance and last but not the least, lack of support and recognition on the part of the government.

According to the Central Statistical Organisation all the unincorporated enterprises and household industries (other than the organised ones) which are not regulated by law and which do not maintain annual accounts or balance sheet constitute the unorganised sector (COS, 1980, p. 135).

According to the Annual Report, Ministry of Labour and Employment, Government of India 2010-11, the term 'unorganised worker' has been defined under the Unorganised Worker Social Security Act, 2008 as a home based worker, self employed worker or wage worker in the organised sector, and includes as worker in the organised sector who is not covered by any of the following acts –

- (i) The Workman's Compensation Act 1923, (8 of 1923),
- (ii) The Industrial Disputes Act, 1947 (14 of 1947),
- (iii) The Employee's State Insurance Act, 1948 (34 of 1948),
- (iv) The Employee's Provident Funds & Miscellaneous Provision Act, 1952 (19 of 1952),
- (v) The Maternity Benefit Act, 1961 (53 of 1961) and
- (vi) The Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972 (33 of 1972).

As per the survey carried out by the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) in the year 2004-05, the total employment, in the both organised and unorganised sector in the country was of the order of 45.9 crore comprising of around 2.6 crore in the organised sector and balance 43.3 crore workers in the unorganised sector. Out of the 43.3 crore workers in the unorganised sector, there are 26.8 crore workers employed in agricultural sector, about 2.6 crore in construction work and remaining in the manufacturing and services. A large number of unorganised workers are home based and are engaged in occupations such as beedi rolling, agarbatti making, papad making, tailoring and embroidery work. Thus, there is a need for direct support to unorganised sector besides defending it against appropriation by organised sector for improving employment, productivity and incomes of the poor.

Social Security : Definition & Issues : Beveridge Committee Report (1942) defines social security as "Freedom from Want" But in practice its provision was confined to only three aspects—Children's allowances, comprehensive health and rehabilitation services and maintenance of employment to avoid mass unemployment. The most authoritative definition on social security emerged from the efforts of ILO (Parrot, 1992) and led to identification of costs of social security provisions. According to the ILO, the term social security has been used to refer to 'the result achieved by a comprehensive and successful series of measures for protecting the public from the economic distress that, in the absence of such measures, would be caused by the stoppage of earnings in sickness, unemployment or old age and after death, for making available to the same public, medical care as

needed and for subsidizing families bringing up young children." The above definition's aim is provisions of relief mainly to workers from particular contingencies and action. The Circumstances which forced the adoption of definition were forgotten and the institutional definition was adopted as the official definition of the ILO. In the process the emphasis by Beveridge Committee Report on 'Freedom from want' was side lined. The net result is that the social security measures are mostly confined to the organised sector worker only.

Social security as a concept has two elements. The first relates to security—security against any insecurity that an individual may face. Such insecurities are not necessarily related to one's status as an employee; they can arise in the course of ones life; and a civilised society must do all that is possible and reasonable to guard against such insecurities. Hence the word 'social'. In a modern community, it is not possible, beyond a point, for an individual to guard himself/ herself against each in security. It is the society of which he/ she is a part that must ensure the necessary safe guards against such insecurities taking place and provide the needed protection should such contingencies arise.

Basically social security cannot be isolated from economic security which takes several forms. For a person in employment, this means both security of employment and reasonable or adequate wages or earnings. For one who is employable and is willing to work but unable to find a job, economic security would also include security of employment. For the one who is 'self-employed', particularly in unorganised sector, economic security would mean availability of regular work in terms of supply of raw materials and collection and sale of finished products, along with adequate remuneration of his/ her effort. Such self employed persons are exposed to the risk of economic insecurity arising out of their 'capital' being lost due to natural calamities and other reasons. They face the risk of losing not only one's earnings but also one's assets. Thus it is the need of the hour to take care of the economic insecurity as one third of the population of the country still lives below poverty line and 90 percent of the work force is in the unorganised sector, without any regularly of employment or earnings. The situation is even worse when we consider the position of women who constitute almost half the population and yet form less than one third of the workforce, bulk of them being in the unorganised sector.

The social security schemes in India cover only a small segment of the organised work force, which may be defined as workers who are having a direct regular employer-employee relationship within an organisation. The social security legislation in India derive their strength and spirit from the Directive Principles of state policy as contained in the constitution of India. These provided for mandatory social security benefits either solely at the cost of the employees or on the basis of joint contribution of the employers and employees. While protective entitlements accrue to the employees, the responsibilities for compliance largely rest with the employers.

In order to take care of the social security and welfare of unorganised workers, two prolonged strategy, i.e. legislative measures and implementation of welfare schemes and programmes have been followed. The Legislative measures include, The Minimum Wages Act 1948, The Workman's Compensation Act 1923, the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961, The Bonded Labour System (Abolition) act, 1970, the Inter State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act 1979, The Building and Other Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act 1996 etc.

The Government has set up Welfare Funds for Providing Welfare measures to the beedi workers, non-coal mine and cine workers. The Funds are used to provide financial assistance to these workers for education of their children, recreation, medical and health facilities, construction of houses etc.

The Ministry of Labour and Employment is administering five welfare funds for beedi, cine and certain categories of non-coal mine workers. The Funds have been set up under the following Acts of Parliament for the welfare of these workers –

- The Mica Mines Labour Welfare Fund Act, 1946
- The Limestone and Dolomit Mines Labour Welfare Fund Act 1972
- The Iron ore, Manganese Ore Mines and Chrome Ore Mines Labour Welfare Fund Act, 1976
- The Beedi Worker's Welfare Fund Act 1976, and
- The Cine Worker's Welfare Fund Act, 1981.

The Above Act provide that the fund may be availed by the Central Government to meet the expenditure incurred in connection with the measure and facilities which are necessary to provide for the welfare of such workers. In order to give effect to the objectives laid down in the above acts, various welfare schemes have been formulated and are under operation in the fields of health, social security education housing, recreation and water supply.

In order to ensure welfare of workers in the unorganised sector which, inter-alia include weavers, handloom workers, fisherman and fisherwomen and toddy tappers, leather workers, plantation labour, beedi workers, the Ministry of Labour & Employment has enacted the *Unorganised Workers Social Security Act, 2008* effective from 16 May, 2009. The Act provide for constitution of *National Social Security Board* which shall recommend formulation of social security schemes viz. life and disability cover health and maternity benefits, old age protection and any other benefit as may be determined by the government for unorganised workers.

The Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojna was formally launched on 1 Oct 2007 to provide smart card based cashless health insurance cover to the BPL families (A unit of Five) in Unorganised sector per annum on a family

floater basis. *The National Social Security Fund* has been set up for unorganised sector workers with an initial corpus of Rs. 1000 crore. This fund will support schemes for weavers, toddy-tappers, rickshaw pullers, beedi workers etc.

Suggestions for Effectiveness of Social Security Programmes : Though India has adopted many promotional and protective social security schemes but they are not very effective. The main problems are insufficient allocation of funds and its inefficient utilization of funds by the government (both centre, state and also NGO's). There is need for more funds for social security programmes in a poor country like India compared to rich western countries and rich developing countries in Asia (Singapore and Malaysia). The state government should allot more funds particularly poorer states like MP, Bihar, UP, Rajasthan and Orissa, often quoted as BIMARU states.

Besides higher allocation of funds, emphasis should be placed on effectiveness of the schemes touching upon efficient utilization of funds and the reach of the same to the poorer sections. There is every need for these promotional and protective programmes of the government to reach the poor and needy. The remedy lies in decentralization, grass root level vigilance, participatory approach by the people, commitment by government officials and political power for helping the poor workers (both in organised and unorganised sectors) to overcome deprivation and vulnerability so as to lead better quality of life.

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